

BLUE ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to examine Blue Economy and sustainable development in Nigeria which is the core objective of the paper. Nigeria is approximately 853 km Atlantic coastline, inclusive of the nutrient-rich Niger Delta, and its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) extending 200 nautical miles, present considerable untapped freshwater, marine, and offshore resource possibilities. The country's fisheries and aquaculture sector employed around 1.48 million individuals as of 2022 and contributed between 1.2 % and 3–5 % of GDP depending on the component marine food systems rose from 0.5 % of GDP in 2013 to 4.5 %. In spite of the high potentials in blue economy, there are gaps and challenges in the sectoral economy, these include; Weak Institutional Framework and Poor Policy integration, marine pollution and environmental degradation, insecurity and piracy in coastal waters and among others. Hence, the paper recommend thus, Strengthen Governance and Regulatory Frameworks, enhance infrastructural and Technological Innovations and maritime Security and surveillance. If these challenges are addressed, Nigeria stands poised to transform its Blue Economy into a central pillar of sustainable development in the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: Blue, Economy, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

The concept of the blue economy has emerged as an economic transformative framework for harnessing the vast potential of ocean and aquatic resources to drive sustainable development, particularly among coastal and riverine nations of the world. The blue economy, as defined by the World Bank (2017), refers to the “sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and jobs while preserving the health of ocean ecosystems.” the core of blue economy as a marine-based industries include fisheries,

aquaculture, maritime transport, offshore energy, and coastal tourism with environmental sustainability, inclusive growth, and poverty reduction.

In Nigeria, with an estimated coastline of about 853 kilometers along the Atlantic Ocean and a maritime domain of approximately 290,000 square kilometers, the blue economy holds immense promise (Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency, (NIMASA, 2022). The country's inland water systems comprising rivers, lakes, and wetlands with its rich aquatic resource base. The Nigerian maritime industry contributes less than 2% to the nation's gross domestic product (GDP), the economic potential of the sector can generate over \$296 billion annually through diversified blue economy activities (Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy, 2023). The Nigerian blue economy has been facing challenges ranging from unsustainable exploitation of marine resources, oil pollution, illegal fishing, habitat degradation, and unregulated coastal developments have historically undermined Nigeria's ocean economy (Obi, 2021).

Other issues include, institutional weaknesses, policy fragmentation, and limited awareness have further stifled innovation and investment in the sector. Sustainable development within the blue economy framework entails a balanced integration of economic productivity, environmental stewardship, and social inclusion. Nigeria, as Africa's most populous nation with over 220 million people (World Bank, 2024), stands to benefit substantially from a well-articulated blue economy strategy. It could enhance food security through sustainable fisheries, reduce youth unemployment via maritime training and job creation, and strengthen climate resilience through coastal restoration and marine ecosystem protection.

Historical Overview of Nigeria's Blue Economy

Before the advent of colonial rule, the peoples of present-day Nigeria had robust economic, cultural, and spiritual connections to their aquatic environments. The Niger Delta, coastal communities along the Atlantic, and riverine settlements inland thrived on fishing, canoe carving, salt making, and trade through waterways. Rivers such as the Niger, Benue, and Cross River served as arteries of commerce and cultural exchange, linking communities across West Africa. Fishing was a principal occupation among communities like the Ijaw, Ilaje, and Itsekiri, utilizing traditional methods such as fish traps, nets, and dugout canoes. Aquatic biodiversity was respected and embedded within traditional ecological knowledge systems, with taboos and customs regulating fishing seasons and areas to prevent over exploitation (Adewumi & Adebayo, 2018). Maritime-related trade also flourished in this period. Notably, the Ijo and Efik communities were prominent in coastal trade networks involving salt, smoked fish, and palm oil. While the notion of a "blue economy" did not formally exist, the sustainable use of marine and freshwater resources was central to pre-colonial livelihoods.

The colonial period (1861–1960) marked a significant transformation in Nigeria's relationship with its marine resources. The British colonial administration developed ports such as Lagos, Port Harcourt, Calabar, and Warri primarily to serve extractive and export-oriented interests. Coastal and inland waterways were further integrated into the colonial economic system to facilitate the movement of raw materials such as palm oil, groundnuts, and timber (Rodney, 1972).

This period also saw the imposition of foreign governance structures that disrupted indigenous aquatic economies. Traditional fishing practices faced neglect, while colonial authorities prioritized the development of merchant marine infrastructure. The Lagos Harbour was dredged and expanded, and the Nigerian Marine Department (later Nigerian Ports Authority) was established in 1954 to oversee marine navigation and infrastructure (Olukoju, 2006). The environmental and economic sustainability of local marine systems was not a priority at this era. Following independence in 1960, Nigeria inherited maritime infrastructure and regulatory institutions from the colonial administration. The early post-colonial years saw an expansion of shipping, oil exploration, and offshore activities. The discovery of oil in Oloibiri in 1956 and its subsequent offshore exploitation transformed Nigeria into a hydrocarbon economy, significantly increasing its dependence on the ocean space (Nwilo & Badejo, 2006).

The blue economy concept began gaining traction in the 21st century as Nigeria faced increasing challenges such as overfishing, pollution, piracy, and oil spills, particularly in the Niger Delta. In response, the Nigerian government initiated efforts to diversify the economy through the development of marine-based sectors like aquaculture, maritime transport, coastal tourism, and renewable ocean energy (Federal Ministry of Transportation, 2021).

In 2019, Nigeria hosted its first-ever international conference on the blue economy, emphasizing sustainable ocean development. The Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) launched initiatives for the protection of marine resources, while the Deep Blue Project was introduced to enhance maritime security in the Gulf of Guinea. This aligns with global frameworks like the African Union's 2050 Africa's Integrated Maritime Strategy and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 14.

Economic gains of Blue Economy

The concept of the Blue Economy encapsulates the sustainable use of ocean, sea, and inland water resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and job creation, while preserving the health of aquatic ecosystems. In Nigeria, Blue Economy contributes significantly to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP),

Offshore Oil and Gas

The offshore oil and gas sector dominates Nigeria's blue economy in terms of revenue generation, contributing over 90% of the nation's foreign exchange earnings. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2022), this sector provides direct employment to around 65,000 Nigerians, primarily in offshore operations, engineering, and logistics. For instance, Okonkwo & Nwankwo (2021) found in their study of host communities in Bayelsa State that youth unemployment remained above 35% despite proximity to oil installations, highlighting a disconnect between resource wealth and livelihoods. Hence, there is need for diversification to the blue economy.

2. Contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The Nigerian maritime sector, a key component of the Blue Economy, contributes significantly to the national GDP. According to the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA), the maritime sector alone accounts for about 5% of Nigeria's GDP,

with prospects for exponential growth through reforms and infrastructure investments (NIMASA, 2021). A study by Olaniyi and Adewuyi (2020) using input-output modeling showed that maritime logistics, offshore oil exploration, and fisheries collectively contribute over \$70 billion annually to the Nigerian economy. This underscores the direct macroeconomic relevance of the Blue Economy in national development planning.

3. Employment Generation and Skill Development

Nigeria's Blue Economy is a significant employer, particularly in fisheries, shipping, port operations, and tourism. The Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (2020) reported that over 8 million Nigerians are directly or indirectly employed in artisanal and industrial fisheries. The Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) employs thousands more across port operations, logistics, and customs handling. The development of port infrastructure and inland waterways can absorb youth unemployment in Nigeria. For instance, the revitalization of the Onitsha Inland Port is projected to create over 3,000 direct jobs and thousands more in related transport and logistics chains (NPA, 2022).

Revenue from International Trade and Port Services

Nigeria's strategic location on the Gulf of Guinea provides it access to international maritime trade routes. According to UNCTAD (2021), over 90% of Nigeria's international trade by volume is carried through maritime transport. Ports in Lagos, Port Harcourt, Warri, and Calabar serve as gateways for import-export activities.

In 2020 alone, the Lagos Port Complex handled cargo valued at over ₦20 trillion (NPA, 2021). Port reform initiatives and automation have improved cargo clearance times, thereby boosting government revenue from customs duties and port charges. Between 2019 and 2021, the Nigerian Customs Service reported an increase in revenue collection from ₦1.3 trillion to over ₦2 trillion, much of it linked to seaborne trade (NCS, 2021).

5. Food Security and Fisheries Development

Nigeria's aquaculture and fisheries sector is a core component of its Blue Economy. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2020) estimates Nigeria's fish demand at 3.2 million metric tonnes per annum, with current local production standing at about 1.1 million metric tonnes, thus creating a huge opportunity for domestic growth and import substitution. According to the Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research (NIOMR) fishery development programs in coastal states (e.g., Bayelsa, Delta, and Akwa Ibom) have led to a 30% increase in household income for artisanal fishers between 2016 and 2020.

7. Energy Diversification and Blue Renewable Resources

The offshore oil and gas sector, though often associated with environmental risks, remains a core component of Nigeria's Blue Economy. The Deep Offshore and Inland Basin Production Sharing Contract (Amendment) Act of 2019 enabled Nigeria to generate an additional \$500 million annually from offshore oil operations (NEITI, 2020). The National Energy Policy (2022) includes blue energy among the future targets for Nigeria's transition to renewable sources, enhancing energy security and reducing dependence on fossil fuels.

8. Regional Integration and Maritime Security

The Blue Economy also enhances Nigeria's role in regional maritime cooperation through bodies like the Gulf of Guinea Commission. Nigeria's investment in the Deep Blue Project, launched by NIMASA and the Nigerian Navy, has significantly improved maritime security, reducing piracy incidents by 77% between 2020 and 2023 (IMB, 2023). This stability increases investor confidence in maritime transport and logistics, enabling smoother regional integration within ECOWAS and boosting trade under the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

Challenges of Blue Economy and sustainable development

1. Weak Institutional Framework and Poor Policy Integration

One of the central challenges to the growth of Nigeria's Blue Economy is the absence of a unified and coherent institutional framework. Various government agencies such as the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA), the Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA), and the Federal Ministry of Environment operate in silos, resulting in policy overlaps, regulatory duplication, and inefficiencies (Adekola & Mitchell, 2021). Nigeria's maritime and coastal governance show that there is a lack of integration between national development plans and sustainable ocean strategies (Uche, 2023).

2. Marine Pollution and Environmental Degradation

Environmental degradation caused by oil spills, marine plastic pollution, industrial discharge, and ballast water contamination presents a serious threat to Nigeria's aquatic biodiversity and coastal livelihoods. According to data from the National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA, 2021), over 4,000 oil spill incidents were recorded between 2011 and 2020, with the Niger Delta being the worst affected. These incidents not only harm fisheries and marine life but also undermine the health and economic well-being of coastal communities.

3. Insecurity and Piracy in Coastal Waters

Maritime insecurity, including piracy, sea robbery, and kidnappings for ransom, continues to destabilize Nigeria's maritime domain. The Gulf of Guinea, which includes Nigerian territorial waters, was identified by the International Maritime Bureau (IMB, 2021) as one of the most dangerous maritime regions globally. In 2020 alone, 95% of all maritime kidnappings in the world occurred in this region. This level of insecurity discourages investment in the maritime sector and limits trade and shipping activities vital to the Blue Economy.

4. Limited Infrastructure and Technological Capacity

The dearth of modern infrastructure such as seaports, shipyards, inland dry ports, and fisheries processing facilities limits Nigeria's ability to benefit fully from the Blue Economy. According to a World Bank report (2020), only 20% of Nigerian fisheries are industrialized, while over 80% operate at the artisanal level using outdated tools. Moreover, poor logistics and weak transportation links further hinder value-chain integration across blue economy sectors such as aquaculture, marine tourism, and shipping.

5. Climate Change Vulnerabilities

Rising sea levels, coastal erosion, and ocean acidification linked to climate change disproportionately affect Nigeria's low-lying coastal areas, such as Lagos, Bayelsa, and Cross River states. The Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMet, 2022) projects that over 35% of Nigeria's coastline is at risk of submersion by 2050 if current trends persist. This environmental vulnerability not only threatens infrastructure but also displaces coastal populations and disrupts marine ecosystems critical to economic and social sustainability.

6. Inadequate Human Capital Development

The Blue Economy sectors in Nigeria are characterized by significant skills gaps, especially in marine engineering, oceanography, fisheries science, and coastal resource management. While institutions such as the Maritime Academy of Nigeria (MAN) have made efforts to train professionals, enrolment and graduation rates remain insufficient. Olaniyi and Akinyemi (2022) indicate that less than 10% of personnel in Nigeria's shipping and port sectors have received specialized technical training, thereby affecting sectoral productivity.

8. Lack of Reliable Data and Ocean Mapping

Reliable data on Nigeria's aquatic resources is limited, and ocean mapping is underdeveloped. Without accurate bathymetric data, marine spatial planning and offshore resource management remain suboptimal. Nwankwo and Akpan (2020) stress that the country lacks a centralized Blue Economy data repository, making it difficult to track resource exploitation, monitor ecosystem health, or measure socio-economic impacts effectively.

Conclusion and recommendations

The Blue Economy in Nigeria holds vast potential as a transformative pathway to sustainable national development, economic diversification, and inclusive growth. Nigeria's extensive coastal and inland water resources spanning over 853km of coastline and about 11 million hectares of inland water bodies offer a platform for job creation, food security, trade expansion, energy development, maritime transport, and biodiversity conservation. Despite these endowments, the full realization of the Blue Economy remains constrained by some challenges ranging from inadequate infrastructure, maritime insecurity, poor governance, environmental degradation, and limited intersectoral coordination. The growing threats of illegal fishing, pollution, piracy, and climate change further undermine the sustainability of marine and aquatic ecosystems, demanding urgent institutional, technological, and legislative interventions. The Blue Economy can contribute significantly to GDP growth, reduce unemployment, and improve livelihoods, especially in coastal communities.

To effectively harness the potentials of the blue economy, the paper made the following recommendations: Strengthen Governance and Regulatory Frameworks Nigeria needs a coherent and enforceable national blue economy policy backed by strong legal instruments. Agencies like the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA), the Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy, and the Nigerian Navy should be empowered to coordinate efforts and enforce compliance with international maritime standards, these will make the blue economy in Nigeria a sustainable gesture.

Enhance Infrastructural and Technological Innovations

The government should prioritize investments in port modernization, inland waterways, cold-chain systems, aquaculture facilities, and marine biotechnology. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) should be encouraged to bridge infrastructural gaps and foster innovation in blue energy, Digital Ocean mapping, and marine resource monitoring should be initiated and sustained within the coastal regions.

Maritime Security and Surveillance To secure maritime trade and offshore investments, Nigeria must invest in modern surveillance technologies, strengthen its naval capabilities, and foster regional cooperation through initiatives such as the Gulf of Guinea Maritime Collaboration Forum (GoG-MCF/SHADE). Effective enforcement against piracy, smuggling, and illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU).

Establishment of Blue Economy Research and Knowledge Hubs Nigeria should invest in marine research institutions to generate local data, forecast ocean trends, and support evidence-based policy-making. Collaboration with universities and international partners can enhance capacity for marine spatial planning and innovation leading to economic sustainability in Nigeria and Africa in general.

REFERENCES

- Adekola, O., & Mitchell, G. (2021). Institutional integration and sustainable coastal governance in Nigeria: A policy analysis. *Marine Policy*, 124, 104365.
- Adewumi, A. A., & Adebayo, I. A. (2018). Traditional fishing methods and the sustainability question: A case study of Ilaje, Ondo State. *Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 13(2), 45–52.
- Ezenwa, N. (2022). Private sector engagement in Nigeria's blue economy: Potentials and challenges. *Nigerian Journal of Development Studies*, 18(2), 88–102.
- FAO. (2020). *Fishery and Aquaculture Country Profiles: Nigeria*. Food and Agriculture Organization.
- Federal Ministry of Marine and Blue Economy (2023). *Strategic Policy Framework for Nigeria's Blue Economy*. Abuja: Government of Nigeria.
- Federal Ministry of Transportation. (2021). *Policy framework on maritime sector development*. Abuja: Government Press.
- IMB (International Maritime Bureau). (2021). *Piracy and Armed Robbery Report*. London: IMB.
- IMB. (2023). *Piracy and Armed Robbery Against Ships Report*. International Maritime Bureau.
- Lagos Ministry of Tourism. (2022). *Blue Economy and Waterfront Development Report*.

- NEITI. (2020). Oil and Gas Industry Report 2019–2020. Nigerian Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative.
- Nigerian Customs Service. (2021). Revenue Performance Report.
- Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA, 2022). Nigeria's Maritime Profile: Blue Economy Potentials and Outlook. Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency.
- Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA). (2023). Blue Economy Policy Brief. Lagos: NIMASA Press.
- Nigerian Ports Authority. (2021). Operational Performance Summary Report.
- NIMASA. (2021). Annual Maritime Sector Report. Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency.
- NIMASA. (2022). Annual Maritime Report 2021. Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency.
- NiMet. (2022). 2022 Seasonal Climate Prediction. Nigerian Meteorological Agency.
- NOSDRA. (2021). Oil Spill Data Dashboard. National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency.
- Nwankwo, U., & Akpan, S. (2020). Marine resource mapping and policy implementation gaps in Nigeria. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 193, 105240.
- Nwilo, P. C., & Badejo, O. T. (2006). Impacts and management of oil spill pollution along the Nigerian coastal areas. *Administering Marine Spaces: International Issues*, 119–127.
- Obi, C. (2021). Marine Pollution and Coastal Resource Management in Nigeria: A Policy Perspective. *Journal of Environmental Policy and Development Studies*, 17(3), 45–61.
- Olaniyi, E. O., & Adewuyi, A. O. (2020). Economic Valuation of Nigeria's Maritime Economy. *Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 16(2), 231–248.
- Olaniyi, R., & Akinyemi, A. (2022). Human capacity gaps in Nigeria's maritime industry: A review of workforce readiness. *Journal of Blue Economy and Coastal Development*, 4(1), 45–59.
- Olukoju, A. (2006). Infrastructure development and urban facilities in Lagos, 1861–2000. Ibadan: IFRA-Nigeria.
- Onuoha, F. (2020). Exploring Nigeria's blue economy for national development. *Nigerian Economic Society Conference Proceedings*, 1(3), 33–49.

- Rodney, W. (1972). *How Europe Underdeveloped Africa*. London: Bogle-L'Ouverture Publications.
- Uche, C. A., Eze, V. C., & Danladi, Y. (2023). Governing the blue economy in Nigeria: Emerging trends and institutional challenges. *African Journal of Policy and Development*, 12(1), 61–78.
- UNCTAD. (2021). *Review of Maritime Transport*. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development.
- United Nations (2015). *Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. New York: UN.
- World Bank (2017). *The Potential of the Blue Economy: Increasing Long-term Benefits of the Sustainable Use of Marine Resources for Small Island Developing States and Coastal Least Developed Countries*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- World Bank (2024). *World Development Indicators*. [Online] Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2020). *Fisheries and Aquaculture in Sub-Saharan Africa: Opportunities and Challenges*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group.